

DISPARITY OF INVESTMENT GROWTH RATES ACROSS REGIONS AND ITS SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONSEQUENCES

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the imbalance in investment growth rates across regions and its socio-economic consequences based on an empirical and analytical approach. The study analyzes the sharp differences in investment growth rates across regions from the perspective of the uneven distribution of economic resources, differences in regional development levels, and their impact on the development of social infrastructure. It is argued that high rates of investment activity in some regions and low rates in others create imbalances in indicators such as employment rates, population incomes, housing construction, and the quality of social services.

In recent years, the growing regional disparities in global and national economic development have sharply increased the need for a deep analysis of investment growth rates across regions. In modern economic theories, investments are considered a key factor in economic growth, but their uneven growth across regions creates problems of social inequality and stability, along with economic efficiency. From this point of view, the regional imbalance in investment growth rates is becoming an issue that requires special scientific attention, not only with its economic, but also with its socio-economic consequences. International scientific research shows that sharp differences in investment growth rates across regions deepen regional productivity disparities and weaken the sustainability of long-term economic growth. In particular, the concepts of regional development developed by the OECD note that the centralization of investment growth concentrates economic activity in limited areas and reduces production and employment opportunities in remote areas [1]. This approach justifies the need to pay special attention not only to overall growth rates, but also to their territorial distribution when assessing investment growth rates.

Also, World Bank studies assess the territorial imbalance of investment growth rates as a factor that exacerbates the differences between infrastructure development, the labor market, and incomes of the population [2]. While high investment growth rates in some regions are accelerating economic activity, the lack of investment in other regions is causing economic stagnation and social problems. This situation indicates the need to reconsider investment policy based on the criteria of territorial balance and social effectiveness.

The social consequences of territorial investment growth rates are also emphasized in the concepts of inclusive development put forward by the UNDP. According to this approach, territorial differences in investment growth rates create significant differences in the level of employment, incomes, housing conditions, and access to social services [3]. As a result, although economic growth is positive in general terms, its social benefits are not distributed evenly across regions.

At the national level, the issue of managing investment processes on the basis of territorial balance has been identified as a strategic task. In the resolutions and decrees adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the integrated socio-economic development of regions, increasing investment growth rates, as well as ensuring their stable and balanced distribution across regions, is identified as a priority [4]. However, practice shows that the imbalance in investment growth rates across regions remains, and this situation creates significant differences in the results of socio-economic development.

Therefore, a scientific analysis of the imbalance in investment growth rates across regions and its socio-economic consequences, identifying the causes of these processes and developing proposals aimed at balancing regional investment policy is an urgent scientific task today.

The effectiveness of regional investment management is empirically analyzed using the example of the Namangan region and its districts. The study was conducted for 2017–2024, based on the volume of investments in fixed capital, their distribution across regions, and macroeconomic indicators reflecting investment efficiency. The main goal of the analysis is to determine the level of regional imbalances in investment flows and to scientifically assess the relationship of this situation to limitations in management mechanisms.

Also, in the process of analysis, special attention was paid to the relationship between the growth of investment volumes and their economic return. In this case, the indicators of investment intensity, the level of territorial centralization and investment efficiency are compared, revealing the impact of institutional and organizational factors in management on real economic results. This approach allows us to determine the investment processes not only from the point of view of quantitative growth, but also their real contribution to regional development.

The changes in investment processes over time, their interregional differentiation and the level of concentration of capital investments are determined. The tabular data show in which regions investment flows are concentrated, and in which regions they are formed relatively slowly, creating a basis for empirical analysis of the spatial imbalance of investments in regional economic development.

The indicator of investments in fixed capital per capita is one of the most important relative indicators in assessing the effectiveness of regional investment management, as it reflects not only the volume of investment resources, but also the degree to which they are fairly and balancedly distributed across regions and population groups. The use of this indicator expands the possibilities for interregional comparisons and serves to determine the degree of centralization of investment flows, institutional priorities, and the effectiveness of local governance mechanisms (Table 1).

1-table.

Investments in fixed capital (annual, growth rate)

Hududlar	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Viloyat	110,2	178,1	131,1	88,0	100,5	104,2	121,3	261,2
Mingbulo	172,4	179,6	75,5	95,1	111,3	117,6	96,3	220,6
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Kosonsoy	154,6	146,7	217,5	51,6	83,7	99,3	120,7	215,1
Namangan	115,6	122,7	117,0	156,2	98,2	131,6	84,6	159,6
Norin	98,8	100,6	202,3	114,2	87,5	119,1	88,0	285,0
Pop	60,5	49,6	156,2	116,2	128,4	79,6	165,1	400,0
To'raqo'rg'on	350,3	452,6	87,0	29,6	79,6	139,9	117,7	167,8
Uychi	99,5	105,6	293,0	85,6	65,9	80,5	198,9	220,9
Uchqo'rg'on	43,0	168,3	85,8	145,3	56,3	109,4	120,7	240,0
Chortoq	112,9	111,5	124,7	137,0	145,7	94,1	197,9	136,3
Chust	104,7	118,6	175,1	215,4	103,1	107,8	151,0	179,5
Yangiqo'rg'on	103,1	92,8	273,9	99,1	94,0	128,3	95,4	263,8
Namangan sh	155,4	140,2	186,4	111,3	112,5	94,5	112,5	341,6

Source: Author's development based on data from the Namangan regional statistics department

The results of the table show that the annual growth rates of investment processes in Namangan region are sharply unstable and disproportionate across regions. The average growth rates across the region were relatively high in 2017–2019 (110.2–131.1%), and in 2020 decreased to 88.0%, which is explained by external economic conditions and a temporary slowdown in investment activity. Although growth rates have recovered in recent years, their sharp fluctuations indicate that the mechanisms for strategic management and forecasting of investment processes are not sufficiently stable. In particular, large differences in growth rates across regions indicate that investment flows are centralized and project-based.

Specific figures across regions further illustrate this imbalance. For example, in Pop district, the annual growth rate of investments in 2024 was 400.0%, in Naryn district this figure reached 285.0%, and in Namangan city - 341.6%. At the same time, growth rates in some regions have decreased sharply: in Namangan district - 84.6% in 2023, in Kosonsoy - 51.6% in 2020, and in Turakurgan - only 29.6% in 2020. These sharp fluctuations indicate that investment activity depends not on regional planning, but on individual large projects and short-term initiatives. As a result, such instability of investment processes reduces the effectiveness of regional investment management and is a serious constraint on long-term sustainable economic development.

Table 2.

Main socio-economic indicators of investments and construction activities in Namangan region (trillion

soums)

Source: Author's development based on data from the Namangan regional statistics department

Data for 2024 show that in the Namangan region, a high level of reliance on external sources prevails in financing investment processes. Only 13.7 percent of investments in the region were financed from the own funds of enterprises and the population, while 86.3 percent fell on the share of received funds. In the structure of these received funds, the share of the state budget was 2.9 percent, bank loans and other borrowed funds was 1.0 percent, and foreign investments and loans was 82.3 percent. This indicates that regional investment activity is mainly provided by foreign capital and external financial resources, while domestic savings and financial independence of enterprises are not sufficiently formed. Such a structure increases the high dependence of investment processes on external conditions, creating institutional risks for long-term stability.

Analysis by region confirms the presence of sharp differences in the structure of financing sources. For example, in Chortoq district, the share of own funds of enterprises and the population was 51.6 percent, and the share of received funds was only 48.4 percent, while in Pop district, the share of own funds was 6.3 percent, and received funds reached 93.7 percent. Also, in Uchkurgan district, the share of foreign investments and loans was 66.9 percent, in Uychi district - 77.9 percent, and in Namangan city - 86.4 percent. The fact that the share of bank loans and other borrowed funds remained in the range of 0.0–1.5 percent in most districts indicates the underdevelopment of regional financial markets and the limited mechanisms for lending to the real sector. As a result, activating domestic financial sources, increasing the role of bank loans, and reducing excessive dependence on foreign investments in managing regional investment processes is an urgent systemic task.

Table 3.

Hududlar	O'z mablag'lari ulushi, %	Qabul qilingan mablag'lar ulushi, %	Chet el investitsiyalari ulushi, %	Boshqaruvga xos tavsif

Viloyat	13,7	86,3	82,3	Tashqi manbalarga yuqori qaramlik
Namangan sh.	9,1	90,9	86,4	Markazlashgan va tashqi yo'naltirilgan
Mingbuloq	20,3	79,7	76,1	O'rtacha diversifikatsiya
Kosonsoy	25,6	74,4	71,6	Nisbatan muvozanatli
Namangan	12,3	87,7	80,7	Tashqi manbaga qaram
Norin	18,8	81,2	79,1	O'rtacha barqaror
Pop	6,3	93,7	91,3	Juda yuqori tashqi qaramlik
To'raqo'rg'on	25,9	74,1	71,0	Ichki manbalar nisbatan faol
Uychi	18,7	81,3	77,9	O'rtacha tashqi bog'liqlik
Uchqo'rg'on	24,3	75,7	66,9	Eng diversifikatsiyalashgan
Chortoq	51,6	48,4	46,7	Eng yuqori ichki barqarorlik
Chust	9,6	90,4	88,0	Tashqi kapital ustun
Yangiqo'rg'on	16,1	83,9	77,8	O'rtacha tashqi qaramlik

The results of Table 3 show that the effectiveness of regional investment management in Namangan region is directly related to the balance between growth rates and the composition of financing sources. Although the average annual growth rate of investments in the region in 2017–2024 was 143.0%, the share of received funds in the financing structure was 86.3%, and foreign investments were 82.3%, and the share of internal sources remained extremely low. This indicates that high indicators of investment activity are formed mainly due to external financial flows, and the mechanisms for mobilizing internal investment potential in the management system are not working sufficiently. In particular, in regions such as Pop, Namangan city and Chust, high growth rates are accompanied by excessive dependence on external capital, which is a significant limitation from the point of view of investment sustainability.

Interregional comparisons show that management efficiency is determined not only by growth rates, but also by the level of diversification of financing sources. For example, in the Chartok region, 51.6% of investments were financed from the own funds of enterprises and

the population, while the share of foreign investments was 46.7%, which indicates that this region has the highest level of internal stability of investment processes. While in the Uchkurgan and Kosonsoy regions, internal and external sources were formed relatively balanced, in the Pop district the share of foreign investments reached 91.3%, creating a high level of external dependence of investment processes. These results scientifically substantiate that the main limitation in managing regional investment processes is not ensuring growth rates, but rather the balanced formation of investment sources and strengthening the role of internal financial resources.

This study was aimed at a comprehensive empirical analysis of the constraints affecting the effectiveness of regional investment management in the case of the Namangan region and its regions. The analysis, conducted on the basis of investment dynamics, the level of investment per capita and the composition of investment financing sources for 2017–2024, made it possible to identify the real results of regional investment policy and systemic problems in management mechanisms. The results of the analysis showed that, although investment activity in the Namangan region is quantitatively high, its territorial distribution and financing structure are not stable and balanced. The differences in the level of investment per capita between the regional center and some districts and relatively weak regions reach several tens of times. Also, sharp fluctuations in investment growth rates across regions indicate that investment processes depend on individual large projects and external financial flows rather than strategic planning. The predominance of foreign investment in the structure of financing sources and the low level of bank loans and domestic savings make regional investment processes highly dependent on external conditions.

At the same time, the rapid increase in the volume of investments is not fully coordinated with their socio-economic effectiveness. Stable results corresponding to investment growth are not observed in housing construction, healthcare and other social infrastructure indicators, which indicates the weakness of project selection, prioritization and effectiveness assessment mechanisms. In general, the existing restrictions in the management of regional investment processes are reducing the economic and social return on investments and are a factor in deepening inter-regional imbalances. This situation makes it an urgent task to revise regional investment policy, activate domestic financial resources and develop systematic measures aimed at increasing management efficiency.

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